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Analysis of economic factors influencing the reproductive behavior of youth

KEYWORDS

reproductive behavior, factors, demography, economic factors

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The relevance of the study is determined by the declining birth rate and population aging in many countries. Studying the influence of economic factors such as income, housing costs, access to education and healthcare helps to develop measures to stimulate the birth rate and address demographic challenges.

The study is aimed at analyzing approaches to reproductive behavior and identifying the main economic factors influencing the formation of reproductive behavioral models.

Materials and methods. The study utilized articles from scientific journals in economics, sociology, demography, and psychology, focusing on the connection between reproductive behavior and economic factors (e.g., Population Research and Policy Review, Journal of Population Economics, European Journal of Population, etc.). The methods included theoretical and comparative analysis of regional, national, and socio-economic differences in reproductive trends.

Results. Economic factors significantly influence the reproductive behavior of youth. Key aspects include material conditions, housing issues, and income level, which substantially impact the decision to have children. A high income level fosters a more positive perception of motherhood, whereas a low income creates heightened expectations regarding the number of children. Housing conditions are also important: owning an apartment motivates planning for several children; however, the decision to have the first child is the most challenging due to the need for preparation and confidence in state support. Economic independence and the balance between material status and the number of children play a crucial role, especially with the growing number of low-income large families. An important factor is population mobility: the aspiration for a better life outside one's home region delays childbearing until stability is achieved. Overall, contemporary reproductive behavioral strategies are driven by the rationality and economic capabilities of young people.

Conclusion. The topic of reproductive behavior encompasses numerous aspects requiring thorough analysis. The complexity of the study lies in the fact that the analysis implies working not only with objective facts but also accounting for personal and psychological characteristics, which significantly complicates the research process. Therefore, it is necessary to continue studying this issue.

FOR CITATION

Received: Sep 11, 2024
Accepted: Dec 2, 2024
Published: Mar 1, 2025

Filippenko, V. A., & Rostovskaya, T. K. (2025). Analysis of economic factors influencing the reproductive behavior of youth. *Economic Consultant*, (1), 76–90. <https://doi.org/10.46224/ecoc.2025.1.6>

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INTRODUCTION

The relevance of the study is determined by the observed decline in birth rates and population aging in many countries. Understanding the economic factors influencing the reproductive behavior of young people can help develop effective measures to stimulate birth rates and address demographic challenges. Economic factors such as income level, housing costs, access to education and healthcare significantly influence the reproductive decisions of young people. Analyzing these factors provides a better understanding of how economic changes affect reproductive behavior and what measures can be taken to stimulate it.

Many scientific disciplines and specialties place significant emphasis on the study of demographic processes. Issues of demographic regulation and development are considered within economics, sociology, political science, biology, and many other fields. Primarily, this interest is explained by the desire to effectively manage the state, monetary flows, and implemented policies.

Demographic processes interact with all spheres of human life, and therefore it is impossible to consider demography in isolation from the social sphere. The theory of demographic transition, developed by A. Landry, is an example of the connection between the biological and the social in humans.

An important element of the demographic process is reproductive behavior, both of the individual and of society as a whole. In this work, reproductive behavior is primarily understood as the set of actions, choices, and practices associated with family planning, pregnancy, childbirth, and child-rearing. Understanding the features and internal structure of this process will allow for a better grasp of its essence and more effective construction of demographic policy.

In this regard, it is important to trace the dynamics of development in approaches to analyzing the factors influencing the formation of reproductive strategies in the population, to determine which specific factors these are and what exact impact they have on individuals.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research materials consisted of articles in scientific journals on economics, sociology, demography, and psychology, dedicated to the analysis of reproductive behavior and its connection to economic factors: Population

Research and Policy Review; Journal of Population Economics; China Population and Development Studies; European Journal of Population; Population and Environment; Reproductive Health; Maternal and Child Health Journal; Genus; Journal of Population Economics, among others.

Methods employed in the study included theoretical analysis; comparative analysis (comparison of reproductive behavior of young people in different regions, countries, or socio-economic groups to identify general trends and specificities).

LITERATURE REVIEW

It is widely recognized that the reproductive behavior of young people is influenced by education, socio-economic status, cultural and religious norms, family values, access to information and contraception, as well as personal attitudes and psychological state.

Economic factors influencing the reproductive behavior of youth include income level, unemployment, economic stability, and the availability of financial resources, which affect decisions regarding marriage and childbearing.

A. V. Larionov identified factors influencing the targeted reproductive behavior of the Russian population. The researcher proved that reproductive attitudes, housing conditions, and income have the greatest impact on the formation of this behavior [1].

S. Wang et al. investigated the extent to which high housing prices acted as a structural constraint on marriage/fertility. According to the Chinese researchers, exposure to information on both demand-side and supply-side housing policies can significantly contribute to positive marriage and fertility intentions among young unmarried people in Shanghai [2].

J. L. Degner notes that rising prices for educational goods and services, housing, and other relevant household expenses have contributed to a later age of first marriage worldwide. Furthermore, declining fertility has been associated with increasing housing costs, as well as with various forms of state intervention [3].

Z. Spéder and L. Bálint concluded that labor market stability (measured by fluctuations in the unemployment rate), price stability, active state involvement, and the prevalence of certain attitudinal conditions contributed to a higher realization of short-term reproductive intentions [4].

W. Luo and X. Zou found that women in regions with a more significant reduction in export tariffs showed a lower propensity to marry, delay marriage, and had a higher probability of marrying more educated partners. The Chinese researchers argue that the reduction in export tariffs negatively affects female fertility primarily by altering the process and timing of marriage formation and has a negligible impact on the sex ratio at birth [5].

J. Yu et al. conducted a conjoint analysis to study fertility potential among Chinese adults. According to the researchers, greater economic resources and the availability of childcare significantly increase fertility potential. Policies aimed at increasing fertility should focus on supplementing economic resources and improving access to childcare [6].

K. Van Hoyweghen et al. studied childbearing preferences and trade-offs between the number of children and the quality of upbringing. An experiment was conducted with 1,000 men and women in rural areas of Senegal and Uganda. According to the authors, improving living conditions and access to infrastructure in rural areas can empower people to make decisions leading to lower fertility. A shift in focus from controlling reproduction to expanding reproductive rights and empowerment, based on preference-based family planning programs, is necessary [7].

S. Wang and H. Dong note that the unmarried population in Singapore remains an understudied part of the working population of reproductive age, which is nevertheless becoming increasingly significant for fertility research due to the rising age of marriage and first birth. The authors attempt to identify the causal effects of flexible work arrangements by manipulating three scenarios: reduced working hours, increased schedule flexibility, and increased workplace flexibility. All three variables positively influence fertility intentions, particularly among women [8].

I. O. Ayodeji concludes that the sustained decline in fertility in South Korea, ongoing since 1960, is projected to persist into the future. The researcher asserts that simply continuing current fertility-enhancing strategies is insufficient. A comprehensive approach that addresses broader societal issues, including work-life balance, gender equality, and reproductive rights, could help create conditions that enable families to make reproductive choices with confidence [9].

A. L. Owen identifies a positive and significant association between the oil boom and increased fertility rates among US teenage girls aged 15–19; however, a more detailed analysis reveals that changing economic and social conditions are the driving force behind this effect. The rise in adolescent female fertility is

largely attributable to an increase in births among white teenagers. The immediate mechanism driving this effect is an increase in the employment share of young men aged 14 to 24 [10].

S. Becker and J. Fanzo link the current challenges of the global food system to fertility levels. The authors propose two future scenarios, demonstrating the necessity of considering alternative population growth scenarios when planning future transformations of food systems [11].

M. Peterson et al. study the impact of climate change in interaction with the social, economic, and cultural conditions that affect the reproductive health of the population in Greenland. Their results show that enhancing communities' capacity to address housing, educational, and economic inequalities is crucial for supporting individual fertility and reproductive health, regardless of the consequences of climate change [12].

K. M. Jylhä et al. found no evidence that environmental concerns had a notable association with fertility outcomes, but many people living in Sweden perceived a connection between childbearing and environmental issues. Most respondents believe environmental considerations should influence people's decisions to have children, based both on the future living conditions of a hypothetical child and the potential environmental consequences of childbearing, and view global population growth as a problem [13].

Social factors influencing the reproductive behavior of youth include family environment, education level, social norms and values, and the influence of peers and media.

J. A. Brown et al. study the childhood socialization experiences of young Black women and their perceptions of how these experiences influenced their attitudes and behaviors regarding sexual and reproductive health in adulthood. The authors identified several themes in their socialization experiences: support for traditional female gender norms/roles; preparation for prejudice; encouragement of ambition and independence; promotion of racial pride; guidance on sexual and reproductive health matters; and limited involvement in sexual socialization [14].

N. Diamond-Smith et al. note that men in India have low levels of knowledge about biology and family planning. Most men wanted to delay the birth of their first child by at least two years; however, less than a quarter had discussed birth plans with their partners or used family planning methods. The main obstacles to participation were work and migration-related commitments [15].

R. L. Barral et al. note ambivalence regarding support for sexual and reproductive health education. Individuals residing in rural Latin American communities in Kansas revealed misconceptions, negative attitudes, and conflicting beliefs associated with the provision of sexual and reproductive health education and services [16].

H. Rim et al. investigate the relationship between perceived gender discrimination in the workplace (WGD) and reproductive intentions. According to the authors, when stratified by childbirth experience, the negative association between increased perceived WGD and intentions to conceive was significant only among women without previous childbirth experience [17].

C. L. Comolli assesses the relationship between changes in the social climate and social uncertainty, and first- and second-order birth intentions, net of economic uncertainty and socio-demographic determinants. According to the Swiss researcher, a deteriorating social climate and its increasing uncertainty correlate with lower and more uncertain intentions for first and second births [18].

V. A. Leocádio et al. point to the weakening/breakdown of the link between marital status and reproductivity in Brazil, as well as an increase in permanent childlessness associated with socio-economic status and women's choices [19].

Psychological factors influencing the reproductive behavior of youth include personal attitudes, maturity level, self-esteem, motivation, and emotional state.

Y. Ren et al. note that in recent years, due to the continuous aging of China's population and declining fertility rates, the country's population has sharply decreased. According to the researchers, gender, age, education level, economic status, household type, number of existing children, and the sex of the first child are associated with the reproductive intentions of young people of childbearing age. The low childbearing intentions among young people of reproductive age in China are constrained by a combination of economic, age-related, and educational factors [20].

K. B. Guzzo et al. found that higher levels of personal economic pessimism and concerns about future relationships were associated with a greater importance placed on avoiding pregnancy in the short term, even after accounting for objective characteristics such as economic hardship, marital status, and other socio-demographic covariates. The authors emphasize that short-term pregnancy avoidance and childbearing postponement represent a potential mechanism underlying the contemporary low fertility rates in the United States [21].

L. Badolato et al. argue that uncertainty is a key factor in fertility decision-making and behavior. The US-based researchers conclude that more socio-economically advantaged women demonstrate greater intensity in their fertility goals. Women who are more confident in realizing their positive intentions and those who hold them more intensely report a greater number of additional planned children and shorter intended timeframes for future childbearing [22].

L. Newmyer et al. found that exposure to relative mortality was associated with increased fertility, despite a slowdown in the pace of childbearing. The authors' results underscore the need to consider the impact of mortality factors when understanding individual fertility behavior, as well as the importance of specific environmental factors, such as the timing of mortality exposure throughout life, for a better understanding of this relationship [23].

Cultural factors influencing the reproductive behavior of youth include traditions, customs, religious beliefs, and social norms that shape attitudes toward marriage and childbearing.

M. Caltabiano, G. Dalla-Zuanna et al. define a significant association between adherence to Catholicism and sexual behavior. Italian researchers found that the decline in the proportion of young Catholics was not accompanied by a strengthening of adherence to Catholic sexual morality: today, religious youth are more similar to non-religious youth than they were at the beginning of the 21st century [24].

M. Tang and J. Hou note that in China, the son preference is weakening, while the daughter preference is gaining momentum. Changing values and intergenerational relationships exert a strong influence on gender preferences and their translation into reproductive behavior [25].

S. H. Chung et al. emphasize the potential influence of non-economic factors, such as religion and the influence of traditional authorities, on changing fertility patterns in industrialized, educated, and low-fertility societies [26].

L. Rahm defines that significant progress in assisted reproductive technologies has led to concerning trends in sex selection, which have compromised gender balance in major countries such as China and India [27].

Thus, the analysis of sources has revealed a multitude of economic factors influencing the reproductive behavior of youth. Income level, unemployment, housing and educational expenses, as well as economic stability significantly

influence decisions regarding marriage and childbearing. The high cost of housing and education contributes to the postponement of marriage and a decline in fertility. Government policies, labor market conditions, and the availability of childcare also play an important role. Regions with more stable economies and active state support exhibit a higher realization of reproductive intentions. To increase fertility, a comprehensive approach is recommended, including improvements in living conditions, gender equality, and the expansion of reproductive rights. Overall, economic conditions are a key factor shaping the reproductive behavior of youth worldwide.

RESULTS

The evolution of approaches to analyzing demographic processes in the context of reproductive behavior.

American demographer F. Notestein introduced the concept of the “demographic transition”, which he interpreted within the context of the evolutionary development of demographic behavior during historical transformation. The scholar was the first to attempt to identify specific stages of demographic processes. This theory sought to establish a connection between social and economic conditions of development.

The transition from one type of population reproduction to another can span more than one generation, during which transformations occur that ultimately produce a new type of population reproduction.

Despite its widespread popularity, this theory has often been criticized. For instance, S. P. Kapitsa [28] and M. A. Klupt [29] have argued that it cannot objectively and exhaustively explain societal processes through the prism of reproductive behavior, as the theory of demographic transition primarily attempts to explain global trends in the demographic agenda. Therefore, M. A. Klupt developed his own theory, which examines the development of demographic processes through the lens of regional characteristics and global transformations in the fundamental institutions of society.

Within the analysis of reproductive behavior in an economic context, numerous ideas and concepts have been developed, possessing varying degrees of empirical verifiability.

G. Becker has developed the idea of the economics of births, where children are perceived as an economic product with specific costs and benefits. He argued that a reduction in the cost of raising children makes it economically advantageous for

families to have more children; however, such an increase in fertility is not observed in developed countries today, rendering the theory untenable [30].

R. Easterlin proposed a theory of fertility fluctuations, which suggested that an increase in fertility was linked to the achievement of a desired level of material expectations, while failure to achieve this level led to a decline in fertility. This theory found support in the United States, but after the 1960s, empirical data no longer confirmed its predictions [31].

In the theory of demographic development within the micro-level economic framework, R. Willis and T. Schultz link the decline in fertility rates to economic factors. Families make decisions about having children based on their financial capabilities. It is important to note that economic factors have a stronger impact on reproductive behavior in less developed countries. In economically developed countries, people are more inclined to seek psychological satisfaction from having children [32].

Researchers who relied solely on economic indicators in studying reproductive behavior overlooked important social and psychological factors influencing individual behavior.

Furthermore, it is important to recall P. Sorokin's theory of social mobility, which is among the fundamental and foundational concepts studying societal transformations from the perspective of changing hierarchies of social statuses and population migration [33].

Based on an account of regional differentiation characteristics, a concept of regional development was formulated. Its authors studied the development of Russian regions and noted the necessity of developing the social sphere as a future foundation for the effective development of a region, including in a demographic context [34].

The theme of regional development is reflected in the theory of regional development, which emphasizes the consideration of local characteristics when designing programs aimed at managing demographic processes. This line of thought was advanced by many scholars, such as Zh. A. Zayonchkovskaya [35], N. V. Zubarevich [36], and others.

N. V. Zubarevich places considerable emphasis on the most effective measures for regional development to reduce the "shrinkage" of Russia's habitable economic space and to foster better development of human capital in the regions, spreading it from major regional centers and urban agglomerations to less developed peripheral settlements [36].

The decline in fertility rates is primarily associated with a reduction in the role of economic and social motives that previously encouraged higher birth rates and larger families in general. Today, it can be argued that psychological reasons predominantly underlie the decision to have children.

Within feminist theory, the issue of reproductive behavior is examined from the perspective of societal perceptions and gender stereotypes, which assign parenting responsibilities exclusively to women.

High consumption standards and elevated lifestyle expectations can also limit the desire to have children, as they require significant resources.

N. V. Kruglov, while studying youth values, identified the most important values, which included family, financial success, a focus on material well-being, as well as personal health and the health of loved ones. Values are not a static structure; on the contrary, they can change over the course of a lifetime. If the value of children for an individual may be low at present, by a more mature age, positions within the value hierarchy can shift, allowing children to occupy a higher place. Consequently, the importance of properly formulating and implementing demographic policy to effectively utilize reproductive strategy must be emphasized [37].

The conducted analysis of theories and perspectives allows for the identification of several groups of key factors influencing reproductive behavior (see Table 1).

Economic factors

The first group encompasses economic aspects. These primarily include material and housing conditions, the overall cost of living, the affordability of purchasing housing if necessary, and the ability to provide children with adequate living conditions and educational opportunities.

Their constraining role is significant in modern society, as an increasing number of people align the timing of childbirth and the number of children with their career progression. Economic motives can be linked to the desire to acquire material benefits or improve one's economic status through having a child.

It is important to note the variable nature of the influence of the material well-being of a family and an individual on the reproductive attitudes of young people. For instance, with a higher income level, young people are more likely to perceive motherhood in purely formal terms, and conversely, as a means to start their own family. However, a reverse effect is observed concerning the standard of living when

this indicator is lower. Young people tend to form higher expectations regarding the average expected number of children [38].

Table 1

Factors influencing reproductive behavior

Group of factors	Factors
Economic factors	Family's material well-being
	Housing conditions
	Housing affordability
	Cost of living
	Migration
	Female employment
	Quality of human capital
Social factors	Ability to provide adequate living conditions for a child
	Government support measures for families with children
	Childness standards
	Urbanization processes
	Accessibility of education
	Emancipation of women
	Gender stereotypes
	Division of household labor
Contraceptive behavior	
Cultural factors	Role of traditions and religion
	Ethnicity
	Influence of media and films on shaping perceptions of family and relationships
	Declining importance of kinship and parenthood, prioritization of marital relationships
Psychological/ personality factors	General need for children
	Desire to become a parent
	Shifting value structures
	Influence of self-esteem and confidence in the future
	Desire for self-realization and self-development
	Importance of family
	Traumatic experience in childhood (divorce of parents, incomplete families, etc.)
	Career importance
	Willingness to have an abortion
	Confidence in the future

Source: compiled by the author

The housing issue is also crucial for young people when planning a family or having children. It is worth noting that when all necessary housing conditions are met, namely owning an apartment with sufficient living space, young people are theoretically prepared to have not just one child, but even two or three.

It is necessary to emphasize that the decision to have the first child is the most challenging for young people. This is because it is a completely new experience that requires preparation in multiple aspects, and by the time of the child's birth, they want to be as prepared as possible. This category of families requires special attention, information about available support measures, and the development of channels for obtaining information so that young people are confident that they can turn to the state for necessary support and assistance with any questions they may have.

Modern reproductive behavior strategies can be viewed as a result of increased rationality in people's behavior. Economic independence is essential for family well-being. There is a noticeable increase in the number of low-income large families, indicating a decrease in material well-being with each subsequent child. Therefore, young people primarily strive to find a balance between the number of children and their material status, which can lead to either foregoing having children or postponing parenthood.

At the present stage, population mobility processes have intensified significantly, which also affects the demographic situation both in the country and in the regions. In search of a better life, young people strive to leave their regions to access quality education, career opportunities, and a higher standard of living. This impacts reproductive behavior, as in such a scenario and with a rational approach to life, the question of having children may be postponed until a reliable foundation for starting a family is established.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The analyzed research and theories in the field of reproductive behavior allow tracing the dynamics of approaches to understanding this process. Each new approach provides a fresh perspective. At present, it can be concluded that reproductive behavior is a complex structure of interrelated factors formed under the influence of both external conditions and the individual's internal world. However, it is impossible to state unequivocally the nature of each individual factor's influence on reproductive behavior due to the psychological and personal characteristics of individuals.

Nevertheless, the main factors remain material security, the ability to provide children with a quality education and decent living conditions, as well as the place of family and children within an individual's value system.

Changes in reproductive strategies are primarily characterized by a less pronounced desire to have children and the predominance of psychological motives for childbirth, although, at the same time, the high importance of family remains in society.

Furthermore, as noted earlier, the decision to have children is influenced by the family's material situation, income, and the presence of savings. In many cases, it is precisely the uncertainty about one's financial situation that acts as a barrier, leading to the postponement of the first child's birth. In this regard, it is important to note the low effectiveness of propaganda promoting family values and childbirth, as family formation in the modern world is extremely variable. Therefore, it is crucial to shape the perception that personal success and starting a family can be combined.

Consequently, it is necessary to continue studying the connection between reproductive behavior and real-world factors for more detailed and comprehensive planning of programs aimed at improving the country's demographic situation.

The study results can be used to develop programs and measures aimed at supporting young families, improving living conditions, and raising the standard of living, which may stimulate the birth rate and improve the demographic situation [39–41].

Analyzing how economic crises and instability affect the reproductive decisions of young people can help develop measures to mitigate negative consequences and support families during difficult times. Studying the impact of already implemented support programs and measures on the reproductive behavior of youth can help assess their effectiveness and identify areas for further improvement.

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The author have declared that no competing interests exist

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Editor: Santosh Kumar Behera. Sidho-Kanho-Birsha University (India)